

Genomic organization of three rice *pdc* genes, the cDNAs, and their expression in response to aerobic and anaerobic conditions. +++ = high induction, ++ = moderate anaerobic induction. UTR = untranslated region.

root tips (Roberts et al 1989). This permits survival under hypoxic (2-4% oxygen) conditions, suggesting a key regulatory role for PDC under anoxia. Furthermore, in maize roots under anoxia, the rate of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis and cytoplasmic pH control are more important in determining survival than are the actual levels of ATP or the energy charge (Xia et al 1995). It would therefore appear that a further enhancement in the activity of PDC should increase the production of ethanol and increase the rate of ATP synthesis under anoxia.

We are cloning *pdc* and *adh* genes from rice. Three genomic clones, *pdc1*, *pdc2*, and *pdc3* (Hossain et al 1994a), and two cDNA clones that correspond to *pdc1* (Hossain et al 1994b) and *pdc2* (Huq et al 1995) genomic clones, respectively, of the *pdc* gene family have been isolated, sequenced, and characterized from rice (IR54) (see figure).

Comparison of the deduced amino acid sequences of the three rice *pdc* genes showed that *pdc1* and *pdc2* are 88% similar and 78% identical, *pdc1* and *pdc3* are 89% similar and 79% identical, and *pdc2* and *pdc3* are 89% similar and 79% identical. The maize *pdc* (Kelley 1989) showed similarity and identity values of 95% and 90% to rice *pdc1*, 88% and 79% to rice *pdc2*, and 90% and 81% to rice *pdc3*. At least four bands were observed from a Southern blot of IR54 genomic DNA when probed with a DNA fragment from the *pdc* coding region. Southern blots with probes specific to the 5' and 3' untranslated regions of differential bands of these cDNAs showed differential bands corresponding to these genes.

Transgenic rice plants with introduced *pdc* construct confirmed by PCR and Southern analysis. Plasmids used were *pdc* 29:35S promoter-*adh* intron-sense *pdc* cDNA1-nos; *pdc* 32:35S promoter-*adh* intron-antisense *pdc* cDNA1-nos; *pdc* 38:actin promoter-sense *pdc* cDNA1-nos; *pdc* 40:actin promoter-antisense *pdc* cDNA1-nos; *pdc* 42:6xARE promoter-*adh* intron-sense *pdc* cDNA1-nos; and *pdc* 44:6xARE promoter-*adh* intron-antisense *pdc* cDNA1-nos.

Genotype trans-formed	Plasmids	Positive plants (no.)	Fertility
IR54	<i>pdc</i> 38	6	Fertile
	<i>pdc</i> 40	2	Fertile
	<i>pdc</i> 29	20	Fertile
	<i>pdc</i> 42	4	3 fertile/1 sterile
Radon	<i>pdc</i> 42	8	8 sterile
	<i>pdc</i> 44	15	3 fertile/12 sterile
	<i>pdc</i> 32	2	Fertile
	<i>pdc</i> 38	4	1 fertile/3 sterile

Northern blotting experiments showed that the *pdc1* and *pdc2* are inducible under anaerobic conditions; *pdc3* did not give any detectable band on a Northern blot. Unlike *pdc1* and *pdc2* genes, *pdc3* does not have any introns and is shorter; it is probably a pseudogene. The *pdc1* promoter has multiple copies of anaerobic responsive-like elements as in the maize *adh* gene.

Deletion analysis of the *pdc1* promoter driving the *gusA* reporter gene was performed to evaluate the anaerobic responsive elements in transformed rice protoplasts. Following incubation under aerobic and anaerobic conditions, transient GUS activity assays indicated the presence of both positive and negative regulatory sequences.

Six plasmid constructs have been made using the rice actin promoter, CaMV35S promoter, and 6XARE (anaerobic responsive element) promoter driving the *pdc* cDNA1 gene in both the sense and the antisense orientations. All of these plasmids have been transformed into rice cells by the biolistic or PEG uptake method (see table). For certain constructs, although many hygromycin-resistant calli were selected and regenerated small plantlets, they failed to grow to maturity. Some of the IR54 transgenic plants did have normal morphological appearance (height, tiller number, seed set) compared with seed-grown plants, but most of the Radon transgenic plants were sterile or produced only a few seeds. Further characterization

of transgenic plants, segregation of the transgenes in the progeny, and their response under submerged conditions are under investigation.

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Molecular implication of submergence tolerance in rice using expressed sequence tags as probes

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Large-scale sequencing of randomly selected cDNA clones was done to investigate feasibility of a method for isolating plant genes. Total RNA used for cDNA synthesis was prepared from suspension cultured cells of rice grown

Schematic representation of the relative amount of mRNA under submerged condition. Numerals represent the relative amounts of transcript as a percentage of the untreated samples: (1) phosphoglucosomerase, (2) phosphofruktokinase, (3) aldolase, (4) triose phosphate isomerase (5) triose phosphate dehydrogenase, (6) phosphoglyceric kinase, (7) enolase, (8) pyruvic kinase, (9) Pyruvic decarboxylase, (10) alcohol dehydrogenase, (11) Dihydropolyl transacetylase (12) isocitric dehydrogenase, (13) succinyl/CoA synthetase, (14) succinic dehydrogenase, (iron-sulfur protein subunit), (15) succinic dehydrogenase (flavoprotein subunit).

under osmotic (6% or 20% sucrose), saline (2% NaCl), or N-starvation stresses. More than 2,000 cDNA clones were partially sequenced and compared with the GenBank and EMBL data bases. This allowed about 10% of the cDNA clones to be putatively identified as particular genes. These results indicate that stress treatment of suspension cultured cells makes it possible to effi-

ciently isolate various types of plant genes.

To examine the usefulness of expressed sequence tags (ESTs) for the study of gene expression in a specific metabolic pathway, we analyzed transcript levels of genes engaged in ATP-generating pathways under submergence stress. We quantified each transcript level of genes associated with glycolysis and alcoholic fermentation

several times under submergence stress. We found two types of induction patterns: Type I and Type II.

Maximum expression of Type I genes occurred after 24 h of submergence. Transfer to aerobic condition or partial exposure of shoot tips to air reduced expression. In the submergence-tolerant rice cultivar FR13A, several Type I genes were highly induced compared with intolerant cultivar IR42. This suggests that Type I genes may play an essential role in the activation of glycolysis and alcohol fermentation under submerged condition.

Transcripts of Type II genes, such as aldolase and pyruvate kinase genes, reached the maximum after 10 h and did not show remarkable decrease by transfer to aerobic condition. These results suggest that expression of Type I and Type II genes is differentially regulated under low oxygen condition.

It would be worthwhile to analyze mechanisms associated with coordinate or differential expression of the genes. This will lead to improved understanding in molecular breeding of means to manipulate a whole metabolic pathway in rice plants. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Mapping of genes responsible for cold tolerance at the booting stage of rice

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Norin PL 8 is a cold-tolerant parental rice line. It was developed by introducing the genes for cold tolerance from a javanica rice, Silewah, into a Japanese cultivar, Hokkai 241. The chromosome segments introgressed into Norin PL 8 from Silewah have been mapped on chromosomes 1, 3, 4, 7, and 8, and the loci on chromosomes 3 and 4 are probably involved in cold tolerance (Saito et al 1995).

The fertility of B_1F_4 plants of Norin PL 8 and Kirara 397 (Kirara 397/Norin PL 8//

Kirara 397) was 0-95% in the field in 1993. The temperature at booting stage was 2-3 °C lower than that in the average year.

We analyzed the restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) patterns and fertility of 47 selected B_1F_4 plants. Fertility of the plants showing Silewah-type patterns for the loci of chromosome 3 or 4 was about 10% higher than for those plants with Hok-

kai 241-type patterns (see table). The results were almost the same as those obtained in a cold water experiment in which plants in a field were irrigated with cold water for about 1 mo, from the early stages of panicle formation to heading (Saito et al 1995), confirming that the loci on chromosomes 3 and 4 are involved in cold tolerance.

Genotype and fertility of B_1F_4 plants^a of Kirara 397/Norin-PL8//Kirara 397 in 1993.

RFLP marker	Chromosome	Fertility (%)		
		Kirara-type	Heterozygote	Silewah-type
XNpb100	3	50.4	59.0	63.8
XNpb345	3	50.5	56.9	63.8
XNpb102	4	50.6	68.4	66.1
XNpb235	4	52.5	65.1	66.8
XNpb177	4	52.5	65.1	66.8
XNpb379	7	51.2	-	66.8
XNpb278	8	58.7	46.0	57.9

^aPlants (n = 47) were selected from 500 plants; different fertility classes are nearly equally represented. The temperature during July and August 1993 was 2-3 °C lower than that for the average year. The fertility of Kirara 397 was 40%.